

THE RISE OF CHORAL ART

Djuraeva Shaxnoza Ulugbekovna

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instructor of BMSM in Andijan

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ABSTRACT

The shape of choral art in Uzbek national music step by step in year by year

It is a wonderful period in the history of Uzbek cultural music by the second half of twentieth century . The important changes with social historical and cultural are celebrated with new term of magnificent creatures that reflects advanced concepts , new executive groups , occurred directions of music creation . Uzbek composers and musicians who generalized its previous progress and made it go ahead , they affected on new variety of musical genres` occur . It is known , There are plethora of achievements in artistic music genres . Uzbek music started to state in World culture. Uzbek composers and music players are taking a part in influential contests and getting awarded with handsome prizes . Therefore , the sharp intensification of choral music means existence of choral execution and art in that period . In a period of musical culture , professional choral art completely statutoried . There are professional chore organisations , amateur chore groups ,

culture entities , education centres and any different kind of chore groups settled . During the composing creation chore music got shaped and developed . From recycled folklor music to a great status and genres , works were created . The accordance of National traditions and World chore arts` achievements might be observed in execution of chore . Composers namely , M. Burkhanov , S. Babayev , I. Akbarov , B. Umidjonov , M. Bafoyev , F. Olimov chore works made a huge contribution in wide evolution of chore art in Uzbekistan . That is why choral art is based on harden , orderly , constituent and precize rules and and it is significant as occurred special executive tradions in modern musical culture . The evelution of choral execution is a result of musical art`s alive process . The important part of spiritual upbringing is choir conducting art. Because art inspires a person to beauty and sophistication . It helps in development of spiritual feelings . It served as a priceless

spiritual force as a team singing during all development of our people . Among the directions of creativity and performance Chore is the youngest but practical process of executive branches in a competent art process . The art of choir in the Republic is formed in the early twentieth century , and in the second half it also developed substantially and firmly . In the 60s and 80 s , the broad development of this art led to the development of its various types . The formation of professional chorus, amateur chore groups , children`s and educational chore centres caused the colorful bareness of the genres , their genres to expand its compound . For the first time in Uzbekistan a professional choral team was organized in 1952 under the Uzbek State Philharmonics . The Academy was 67 people in the team called Choral Capella . Historical monuments provide information on choral works in ancient Egypt , Vavillan and India . The choral art has played an important role in ancient Greece . The team participant in the Choral Theater in the Antique was a group of actors to sing together and explain to dramatic cases , the movement of heroes . Choral art was associated with religious-prayer ceremonies and palace holidays . The word `` uneducated `` meant `` unable to sing `` in Greece . The Great Greek Philosopher Platon found choral music as a leader art of music . To date , a system of teaching the Choral conductor is formed , in which musical education is carried out continuously . A conductor is given several assignments to learn choral execution . Improving the most bases of the elements of conductral technique ; development of full analytical comments of the conducting repertoires . Note that new works , analytic skills and adjusted folk songs for

choral conductor. Practices based on natural speech tone , the sound parties are semi - cloed and expressive microratic skills on the ways of voice formation ; - A good study of the conductor, it is necessary to do a number of work , such as improving the skills of piano fortepia . The choral theater , which is the new direction of executive in the third renaissance of the new Uzbekistan , is now the formation and development , scientific practical researches are being carried out in further understanding and clearly to the audience . As a result of the research of modern choral executives , great changes are taking place in the traditional implementation of chore today . These changes are of course to find new ways to make audience affect the listeners . Currently , great attention is to unite the genres of chores , that is , aimed at theatricalification by the masters of choir . Search for new forms of choir on the stage and its new forms of development of the stage location . In the choir groups of different ages musical theatres are of special importance . This process helps not only to think freely of the choir artists , but also to deeper the essence of the work done . Of course , in the repertoir of each qualified , perfect masters , which is fluent in this profession , there will be interesting musical programs for choir groups at different ages . These programs remain one of the great style of theatrical , thoroughly elements in illuminating the work without understanding text . This , in turn , makes the work to be performed on the stage . Common question , by the way , what is the choir theatre ? In terms of answering this question, we consider how choir theatre entered to performance of choir . It is advisable to place analyzes in the executive composition of choir , stage and carry out

its important , to state the performance and the elements necessary to hear . In the art of choir performance developed over the years , changes are taking place in the execution of a choir team , consisting of a traditional choir artists in stage . Under the influence of choir theatre , this multiple choir artists are missing and increasing art in the stage , the choir artist is involved in the scene actions . As a result , execution of choir causes various opinions by experts that the volume of votes is becoming kamer performance , sometimes the choice as solo format . Experienced professionals are describing their opinions without approving this process . Modern young choir masters face the difficult task of developing the emerging choir theatre in modern spirit based on the traditions of choral performance . At the same time , they should try to perform it perfectly , choosing the unusual form of the choir , the various stage movements with a delicate taste for the work being performed . To date , the choir has conveyed the artistic idea of the work to the audience only through sound . The movements that are currently being staged are giving the

audience a clearer understanding of the artistic process . As mentioned above , the choir not only performs in the center of the stage , but in some cases from the audience hall , from different corners of the stage , promoting choir performance based on a piece of music . In 2019 , the initiative of the Department of Choir Conducting of the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan held a concert entitled “ National Melodies “ . In turn , the potential of the conductor or choirmaster in organizing these processes in order to increase the popularity of choral art is certainly lacking . An important factor in this involvement of professionals such as the director of the ballet master . If it is planned to carry out a certain creative process without experts in the field , all the responsibilities and difficulties in the work process will fall on the choir master . The effectiveness of this process depends on the knowledge and potential of the choir master .

P.s In the rapidly developing Uzbek national music , the art of choral performance is facing its modernization and is developing and shaping with the times.

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